

PLAN OF ACTION AGAINST WILDFIRE

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1. The California Governor or Los Angeles Mayor can strike a deal with the nearby State to borrow their 50% to 75% firefighters and firetrucks. The remaining 25% to 50% will not be borrowed in case there are emergency fire in those nearby States.

In some locations within the State, the firefighters and firetrucks only experience a certain number of fire cases every month. Borrowing 50% to 75% can be a good strategy to help the wildfire problem in a specific location.

Those with historically no fire cases in the past three months, they can borrow as high as 60% to 75% resources. Cases per fire department.

Travel time is less than 2 to 3 hours only.

2. The President of the United States must issue an executive order to require the initial 100 government helicopter to go to the current wildfire.

There are more than 5,000 helicopters owned by the United States:

- a. **2407** available Bell H-13 Sioux (Light observation helicopter)
- b. **2000** available Hiller OH-23 Raven (Multipurpose light helicopter)
- c. **1102** available Sikorsky H-19 (Utility Helicopter)
- d. **More than 16,000 available** Bell UH-1 Iroquois (Utility Helicopter)

Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_United_States_military_helicopters

Start with at least 100 IDLE GOVERNMENT HELICOPTERS, and gradually increase it as needed. Additional 10 helicopters can be used to transport human resources such as tree cutters, and volunteers, and other resources such as tree cutting tools.

3. The President of the United States must issue an executive order to require all the tree cutters in the United States to go to the nearest City or Town Hall. When there are at least 5 tree cutters, they will be picked up by the above helicopter to the Los Angeles Country near wildfire.

Their minimum per hour rate shall be 150% to 200% of their standard rate since this is emergency situation. If they can work with their standard rate for volunteerism, then that would be great. We need to help them, and their tools, to go to the place they needed them most.

4. The California Governor or LA Mayor can use their power to allocate initial maximum of 25% of their annual funds for the following:

- a. Fuel for the above helicopters (at least 100 helicopters). The Governor or Mayor must strike a deal to the nearby gasoline station, or gas truck to fuel the helicopters.
- b. Operations manager, project manager, or any expert with at least five years' experience. There must be one accountable person for each wildfire. They can work together with the head of fire departments.

Mapped: Los Angeles wildfires (Datawrapper/ The Independent)

For big wildfires such as Palisades and Eaton, hiring of at least FOUR project managers.

Each project manager can be accountable to the northern, eastern, southern, and western part of the wildfire.

He must plan the logistics for the firefighter, firetruck, helicopter and fuels. He must also plan in cutting the trees in the projected path of the wildfire.

The President can also require all the uniformed officials and volunteers with strong physical attributes to help the tree cutters. Cutting and removing trees can create a gap, reducing further progress of wildfire.

The funds of the LA and California is enough to fuel the operations of more than 100 helicopters to stop or slow the wildfire. I imagine every 30 seconds, there would be a systemize helicopters showering the wildfires.

Why helicopter? Faster than trucks in refilling water. They can just get the water in the nearest body of water and shower it into the wildfire. The rate of showering water should be fast enough to stop the wildfire.

The cost of wildfire damage is far greater than the fuel cost for helicopters. There must be no spending limit on fueling the more than 100 government helicopters. And besides, the human lives that can be saved by stopping this wildfire is far more valuable.

References:

Independent. (2025, January 12). *LA wildfires map: Where are the fires in California and where will they go next?* [Image]. The Independent.

<https://www.independent.co.uk/news/world/americas/la-wildfires-map-kenneth-palisades-eaton-where-next-california-b2677154.html>

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